

Short name	Political development	Long name	Political development for expediting CC(U)S
Geographical scope	National level, international level		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	Currently, two main factors have been changing the political landscape vis-à-vis CC(U)S in Europe: meeting the climate goals set by the EU and war. Some of the major European countries are lagging behind in order to meet the climate goals; hence, seemingly, they need to consider all possible alternatives ¹ . Furthermore, after the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the whole process of the energy transition in Europe is under shadow for the seemingly mid-term, while the approach to energy security and security of supply needs to be revisited. In this light, CCS is going to receive more attention as an option to secure energy supply from undesired alternatives like fossil fuels for the short-term and also biomass while curbing CO ₂ emissions.		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	Currently, several countries in Europe, such as a couple of the Nordic ^{2 3} (e.g. Sweden and Denmark), Baltic States ⁴ and Poland ⁵⁶ , have revisited their policies against CC(U)S. These countries are gradually shifting towards supporting CC(U)S to reduce their CO ₂ emissions while securing supply via lesser-desired alternative fuels.		
Other issues this affects	Social acceptance will be affected by political will and favorable policies		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Euractiv. (n.d.). Germany's CO₂ emissions stagnate despite renewables expansion. https://www.euractiv.com/section/climate-environment/news/germanys-co2-emissions-stagnate-despite-renewables-expansion/ • Vangkilde-Pedersen, T., & Skovbjerg, H. (2022). Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) - the Danish Perspective. Danish Energy Agency. https://uploads-ssl.webflow.com/6183d750c2a4a2d74e966763/6234496d3d8d9d691f51ec2c_CCS%20-%20the%20Danish%20Perspective%2C%20March%202022.pdf 		

¹ For instance Germany: <https://www.euractiv.com/section/climate-environment/news/germanys-co2-emissions-stagnate-despite-renewables-expansion/>

² Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) - the Danish Perspective: https://uploads-ssl.webflow.com/6183d750c2a4a2d74e966763/6234496d3d8d9d691f51ec2c_CCS%20-%20the%20Danish%20Perspective%2C%20March%202022.pdf

³ Statens Offentliga Utredningar: Vägen till en klimatpositiv framtid <https://www.regeringen.se/rattsliga-dokument/statens-offentliga-utredningar/2020/01/sou-20204/> (2020), Accessed 9th Jan 2023

⁴ Assessment of current state, past experiences and potential for CCS deployment in the CEE region: Latvia <https://ccs4cee.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/CCS4CEE-Latvia.pdf>

⁵ Assessment of current state, past experiences and potential for CCS deployment in the CEE region: Poland: <https://ccs4cee.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/CCS4CEE-Poland.pdf>

⁶ The Polish Recovery Plan: a careful step toward energy transition: <https://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/en/analyses/the-polish-recovery-plan-a-careful-step-toward-energy-transition/>

[%20the%20Danish%20Perspective%2C%20March%202022.pdf](#)

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